

GLOBAL DEVELOPMENT AND YOUTH ETHICS

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Abstract: in our country, special attention is paid to strengthening the intellectual and creative potential of young people, the formation of moral culture among young people. After all, one of the most important tasks of today is the upbringing of harmonious, purposeful and creatively thinking young people with modern knowledge and skills who are able to take responsibility for a decent future of the country.

The article philosophically explored the issues of youth ethics and the formation of moral culture in the process of global development.

Keywords: global development, modernization, society, youth, ethics, moral culture, moral education.

While globalization occurs in one corner of the world of socio-economic and political processes, the perception of this process, echoing in other parts of the world, is mainly manifested in young people, requiring constant attention to this issue. In this, the acceleration and dynamics of historical changes become complex processes.

Globalization as a multilevel and multi-faceted system today is penetrating into the peat spheres of society, which can be differentiated and separated from each other based on new terms according to their respective fields. For example: Global Communication, global integration, global economy, global politics, global culture, global Science, global Education, global Language, global lifestyle, global cooperation among young people, global problems of young people, etc.

Of these, it is permissible to talk about positive and negative manifestations of the process, if we talk about global progress and youth ethics, which are directly related to the topic and form the basis of the research we are studying. Globalization

is manifested on the one hand as a factor strengthening the processes of unification and integration of World Youth, increasing its level of well-being, accelerating the economic-political processes of states, activating the exchange of technological scientific and cultural achievements of countries and peoples, on the other hand, as a factor generating conflict situations between the peoples of the world.

Social progress is a continuous process that is constantly updated and improved, at the basis of which the criteria for assessing the values of the examination also change. Because, in the assessment of values, the interests of social forces at a certain stage of development are also of certain importance.

“Philosophers have approached the issue of values and their role in the life and development of society from an ontological, gnoseological, heuristic and worldview point of view, trying to reveal the socio-political, cultural-educational and educational significance within the requirements and capabilities of their time”[1, 322]. Values are a positive product of the development of society, the end of the development of material and spiritual resources, human maturation, which also plays a great role for the future.

The socio-spiritual development of society is inextricably linked with a person's worldview, his moral consciousness and forms of thinking. Throughout the development of society, a person reveals a complex of different abilities. All of them manifest themselves in the process of independent human labor activity and the assimilation of knowledge created by man in the era of historical development. As a result, special and general abilities are distinguished in relation to various manifestations of activity. The higher a person's special abilities, the more it is a sign of general giftedness. Intellectual culture requires the study of the characteristics of human intelligence and its structural components, as well as special knowledge about them.

Intellectual culture is a level of personal development characterized by a measure of mastering spiritual wealth and representing a combination of education, independent thinking, understanding the priority of universal values, seeing

phenomena in contradictions and the ability to evaluate them, active desire and ability to learn and replenish knowledge, creative approach to any business.

Currently, scientific, sociological, especially philosophical studies are being carried out on improving the philosophical aspects of the formation of intellectual culture in the world, as well as on the formation of an axiological attitude to this process.

“For this reason, the problem of values, new precepts of Social Development and the search for other worldview goals become the main tasks of spiritual renewal of society. Today, scientists from different countries almost unanimously note that humanity can overcome environmental and other global problems only if the transition to a different civilization is carried out, built in accordance with other values”[2].

Youth culture is one of the most difficult phenomena. This is evidenced by the fact that until recently its very existence was questioned. Nowadays, the number of doubters about its availability has become insignificant, but the problems and difficulties associated with it remain.

It is known that morality, as a social consciousness, represents the system of behavior, behavior, emotion and mutual Real relations between people, formed over the centuries by a particular people, nation or association. Morality also has a universal nature, which ensures harmonious compliance of the nation with the requirements of the general community as a relationship of a particular people to the environment, to people and to oneself.

The education and development of the spiritual moral culture of youth is the most important task of the state and society in Uzbekistan. The values inherent in young people and the elderly, men and women, people of different professions are also spirituality, which in essence serves for society and human perfection. In this sense, the organization of youth education with spiritual and moral values is important both from the theoretical and practical side. Because national values are the main factor in bringing an individual to adulthood. The content and specific methods

of using national and universal values in the educational process are expressed in the educational and moral works of Eastern thinkers.

Knowledge of the world of values and spirituality and its practical study are important in increasing the social activity of young people, as well as in the formation of their moral culture. The essence and significance of each value is determined on the basis of the possibilities of knowledge of the phenomena of Nature, Society and the spiritual world, scientific generalization, influence on social and spiritual progress.

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